

Notes on the protoconchs of Mediterranean and West African *Cabestana* specimens (Gastropoda: Ranellidae)

Apuntes sobre la protoconcha de ejemplares mediterráneos y oeste-africanos de *Cabestana* (Gastropoda: Ranellidae)

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ABSTRACT

Well-preserved protoconchs of European and North African specimens of *Cabestana* are compared and illustrated. No appreciable difference was observed in protoconch morphology between a specimen of the usual Mediterranean morph of *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767), and specimens of the Northwest African morph referred to as *Cabestana dolarium* (Linnaeus, 1767), therefore reinforcing the hypothesis that the two names are synonyms.

RESUMEN

Se ilustran y se comparan protoconchas bien conservadas de ejemplares de *Cabestana* de Europa y Norte de África. No se observaron diferencias apreciables en la morfología de la protoconcha, entre un ejemplar del morfo mediterráneo habitual de *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767), y las muestras del morfotipo del noroeste de África conocido como *Cabestana dolarium* (Linnaeus, 1767), respaldando por lo tanto la hipótesis de que ambos nombres son sinónimos.

INTRODUCTION

Gastropods of the family Ranellidae, like most Tonnoidea, are known to have, in most species, a long-lived planktotrophic larval stage and therefore a large, multispiral protoconch (LAURSEN, 1981; BEU, 1998). However this protoconch is rarely preserved in adult specimens due to erosion. The degradation of the protoconch is to be expected, taking into account that these are large species and live for several years, but it is facilitated by the fact that in many species it is poorly calcified (PECHENIK, SCHELTEMA & EYSTER, 1974) and degrades rapidly. An initial conchiolin protoconch

in planktotrophic tonnoideans is only secondarily filled with shell material (WARÉN & BOUCHET, 1990). For these reasons, it is difficult to obtain specimens of ranellids in which the teleoconch is sufficiently well grown as to allow a safe identification of the specimen, and yet the protoconch is still well preserved. Without meeting this condition, relating a particular protoconch to an adult may remain tentative and is subject to errors.

Currently, only one species of the genus *Cabestana* Röding, 1798, namely *C. cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) is recognized in

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European and neighbouring seas. Nevertheless, it has been repeatedly suggested that *C. dolarium* (Linnaeus, 1767) could be a different species (e.g. PALLARY, 1903; 1920: 43; NORDSIECK & GARCIA-TALAVERA, 1979: 116-117). Beu (2010: 119) selected *Cabestana cutacea* as the valid name to be used for the species named both *Murex cutaceus* and *M. dolarium* by LINNAEUS (1767), were they to be considered synonymous. The two morphotypes are illustrated and compared herein, with notes on their distribution.

Reports on the protoconch of *Cabestana* are scarce. BARNARD (1963) illustrated a protoconch attributed to *Cabestana dolarium* from Algoa Bay, South Africa, and TOSCANO & CRETTELLA (1991) provided scanning electron micrographs of a protoconch of *Cabestana cutacea* from Naples. RAMÓN (1991) reported on the early larval stages of the species, but she did not succeed in rearing the larvae to the later stage preceding metamorphosis.

This note reports on specimens of the genus *Cabestana* collected on the coast of Western Sahara by the second author with a protoconch in an unusually pristine state, and discusses the bearing of this finding on the taxonomy of Eastern Atlantic and Mediterranean species of this genus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Twenty eight specimens of *Cabestana* were collected from tangle nets belonging to coastal fishing boats at La Sarga (23°38'N, 15°59'W) near Dakhla, Western Sahara. The largest specimen is 46 mm high, but many specimens are smaller and some of them retain the protoconch in an exceptionally good state of preservation. All the specimens were collected from residues of cleaning tangle nets next to small fishing boats stranded of the beach; all boats operate very close to the stranding point. Some live-taken specimens were embedded among clusters of sea squirts, among which they were barely visible.

The molluscan collection in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle was scree-

ned for further specimens of European or African specimens of *Cabestana* with preserved protoconch. A specimen from Naples, from the collection gathered by Petit de la Saussaye for his checklist of European Mollusca (PETIT DE LA SAUSSAYE, 1869), was selected and is here also illustrated.

RESULTS

The specimen in the collection of Petit, in MNHN (Figure 1 A-C), corresponds to the morphotype generally agreed on (e.g. GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI, PUSATERI, PALMERI & EBREO, 1997; FISCHER, 2005; DONEDDU, TRAINITO & MAČIĆ, 2015) as representative of Mediterranean *Cabestana cutacea*, with quite a high spire and a varix opposite the aperture. The specimen was in the process of adding a shell increment when collected, as indicated by the lack of thickening of the aperture.

Our specimens from Western Sahara (Figure 1 D-K) all belong to the low-spired morph, with no intermediate varices on the shell, generally identified (e.g. PALLARY, 1903; FISCHER, 2005) as *Cabestana dolarium*.

In both cases, protoconchs have the exposed part 1.2 to 1.4 mm high and 1.45 to 1.55 mm in diameter, with about 3.25 moderately convex whorls. The protoconch-teleoconch transition is abrupt, and marked by a simple edge without a sinus. The surface, from the end of the second whorl to the third whorl, is marked by minute bristles arranged in neat oblique lines (about 8 such lines from suture to suture on the third whorl); on the final part of the protoconch the bristles become more widely spaced and tend to align parallel to the suture.

The teleoconchs are quite different. The specimen from Naples has quite a high spire (the last whorl being 66% of total height), has a pronounced varix opposite the outer lip, and has moderately elevated cords on the last whorl. The specimens from Western Sahara are all low-spired (the last whorl being 73%

Figure 1. *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) from Naples, coll. Petit, MNHN Paris, actual height 32.5 mm. A: shell; B: protoconch, light photograph; C: scanning electron micrograph. This is the usual Mediterranean morphotype.

Figura 1. *Cabestana cutacea* (Linnaeus, 1767) de Nápoles, coll. Petit, MNHN París, altura real 32,5 mm. A: concha; B: protoconcha, fotografía óptica; C: micrografía electrónica de barrido. Este ejemplar corresponde al morfotipo mediterráneo habitual.

to 77% of the total height), without any varix except at the outer lip of adult specimens, and have strongly elevated spiral cords on the last whorl.

DISCUSSION

The protoconch reported by BARNARD (1963: 20, fig. 3g; 29-31) was described as smooth, with 3.5 whorls, 2–2.5 mm high and 2–2.25 mm in diameter. Whereas the number of whorls is comparable, both the size and sculpture are discrepant and suggest that a different species is involved. Furthermore, Barnard noted that the juvenile specimen with the protoconch “had the lirae much less well developed (cingulate) than the 6 juveniles from Natal, which are normal”. From this we conclude that the protoconch figured by Barnard is not conspecific with our specimens from Western Sahara. Whether this means that two different species, one north-west Africa and another from South Africa, have been confused under the name *C. dolarium*, depends on whether the Algoa Bay specimen was correctly

identified, so this cannot be settled at present. We attempted to contact South African Museum to check whether Barnard’s specimen could be located, but this inquiry was not answered.

Figure 2 of TOSCANO & CRETELLA (1991), also representing a specimen of *C. cutacea* from Naples, shows a protoconch comparable in size and shape but smooth, with a deeply incised suture, suggesting that the primary outer conchiolin layer of the protoconch has been dissolved (as shown by WARÉN & BOUCHET, 1990). This may be an artefact, as the specimen was reported to have been cleaned in 5% sodium hypochlorite, a very aggressive treatment; this also indicates that the prickly surface texture of our protoconchs is part of the periostracum.

The question of whether South African populations are the same as “*Cabestana dolarium*” from north-western Africa therefore remains open. Should these prove specifically distinct, it is unclear whether the name *Cabestana dolarium* should apply to one or the other. Both *C. cutacea* and *C. dolarium* were described from unknown locality.

Figure 2. A-F. Specimen from Dakhla, morphotype corresponding to *Cabestana dolarium* (Linnaeus, 1767), actual height 23.7 mm. A, B: shell; C: operculum, actual height 8.3 mm; D: protoconch, light photograph; E: scanning electron micrograph; F: detail of the protoconch whorls showing periostracal bristles. G-I. Juvenile specimen, same locality and morphotype, actual height 20.0 mm. G, H: shell; I: protoconch, light photograph.

Figura 2. A-F. Ejemplar de Dakhla, morfotipo correspondiente a Cabestana dolarium (Linnaeus, 1767), altura real de 23,7 mm. A-B: concha; C Opérculo, altura 8,3 mm; D: protoconcha, fotografía óptica; E: micrografía electrónica de barrido; F: detalle de las vueltas de la protoconcha mostrando las cerdas periostracales. G-I. Ejemplar juvenil, misma localidad y morfotipo, altura 20 mm. G, H: concha; I: protoconcha, fotografía óptica.

Murex cutaceus was stated as "Habitat" (LINNAEUS, 1767: 1217); *Murex dolarium* was described with habitat "In Oceano" (LINNAEUS, 1767: 1223), a wording quite unusual in Linnaeus' work where in most cases a particular ocean is specified. The specimen of *M. dolarium* was indicated as obtained from Johan Henrik Ferber, a highly regarded pharmacist, and member of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, but this does not shed any light on its possible geographical origin. Specimens of both nominal species are still extant in the Linnean collections in London (DODGE, 1957: 179; photographs of the specimens available online at <http://linnean-online.org>) and in Uppsala (WALLIN, 2001: 76). For *Murex dolarium*, the Uppsala specimen is more likely to be authentic: in a letter dated October 5, 1759, Swedish physician Carl Magnus Blom wrote to Linnaeus that Johan Henrik Ferber in Karlskrona has a large collection of shells...; he further wrote that Ferber's sons will bring the collection to Uppsala in order for Linnaeus to arrange it and that Linnaeus is free to keep the shells he finds most interesting (quoted from The Linnean Correspondance website <<http://linnaeus.c18.net/Letter/L2605>>). The three specimens in Linnean Society of London have no connection to Ferber and may be subsequent to the publication.

From our material it can only be concluded that protoconch morphology does not provide any character allowing to differentiate the Mediterranean *Cabestana cutacea* and the Northwest Atlantic *C. dolarium* morphs. There remains a clear morphological gap (see comparative illustrations in FISCHER, 2005) but this could be explained by the fact that

there are two discrete areas where *Cabestana* is relatively abundant, one along the French and Italian coasts of the Western Mediterranean (DONEDDU ET AL., 2015: Fig. 1), where the usual Mediterranean morph predominates, and another one along the coast of north-western Africa between Rabat and the western Sahara (PALLARY, 1920 and our observations) where the species is unusually common and *C. dolarium* morphotype predominates. In between, in the westernmost Mediterranean, strait of Gibraltar and European Atlantic Ocean, the species is exceedingly rare and findings are probably the result of vagrant larvae that successfully settled and grew up, without forming persistent populations that can ensure gene flow between the aforementioned areas. Nevertheless, a single Mediterranean-type morph was found (J.M. Morel, pers. comm.) together with abundant *C. dolarium* morphs at Souira Kedima (32°02.4'N, 09°20.7'W) near Safi, on the Atlantic coast of Morocco, and occasional *C. dolarium* morphs are found as far north as Tangiers, Morocco (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011: 276, lowermost figure), indicating that some limited exchange may exist.

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